

SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF ETHNIC IDENTITY IN PERSONS BORN IN HETERO-ETHNIC FAMILIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8395110>

Abstract: In the article, the study of the ethno-cultural identity of different peoples is traditionally one of the methods of studying the development and formation of the individual. In general, ethno-cultural identity is understudied, although it has attracted the attention of a number of researchers in the last three decades. Children born in inter-ethnic marriages have specific psychological characteristics and difficulties in developing ethno-cultural identity.

Key word: Ethnic identity, family, nation, intercultural, gender approach, intercultural, family relations.

There are historically 2 approaches to research in ethnopsychology: ethnological psychology (or psycho-anthropology) and cross-cultural (comparative cultural psychology). According to the content of the first approach, culture-specific analytical units and terms are used in the study of the mental characteristics of the carriers of one culture. The phenomenon under study is revealed gradually, in this process the researcher should join a religious group, reconstruct his behavior and habits, and become a member of it. Hypotheses are not possible: According to the content of the second approach, studying the psychological life of two or more ethnic groups with the desire to explain intercultural differences and similarities, using units of analysis, is considered free from the influence of foreign culture. It is possible for the researcher to take the position of an external observer with the desire to distance himself from the studied ethnic groups, to preliminarily construct the psychomethodological structure of the research and the category for its description, and to put forward hypotheses.

The research is carried out in various areas: general psycho-cognition, memory and thinking characteristics, industrial psycho-problems of labor organization and management, youth psycho-perception methods among different peoples, socio-psychological aspects of the behavior of people belonging to different ethnic groups. learns its laws, which is reflected in the psychological behavior of communities. Usually, ethnopsychological research is determined by practical needs. The following types of ethnopsychological studies have been determined based on the many researches of scientists. Standard 1 - does not initially include cross-cultural comparisons. Object, national consciousness or sense of identity, national values and orientations, needs and motives; characteristics of auto- and hetero-stereotypes, ethnic relations, traditions, customs and traditions, characteristics of the behavior of representatives of certain nations and peoples.

2- cross-cultural - study of psychological and socio-cultural characteristics of individuals conducted in parallel in several groups of people of different nationalities or in groups where representatives of different nationalities are gathered together.

3- historical and epistemological approach - studying the origin of nations using historical analysis, content analysis, factor analysis and other researches, summarizing various data and other methods. It is used when direct contact with representatives of a

certain nationality is impossible (analysis of historical, political, archival sources). When conducting ethnopsychological research, the researcher's adherence to several ethical and confidential principles serves to guarantee the reliable output of the research results. In particular, according to the first ethnopsychological ethical principle, taking into account various factors of the formation of the ethnic community and its psychology - it indicates the study of the national psyche as a product of history, economy, political and cultural development and other conditions in which this ethnic community lives for a long time.

The second is to analyze non-governmental non-profit organizations of representatives of one ethnic group together with the manifestation of other characteristics - aimed at understanding how their social and individual consciousness is related to the national, class, professional, age characteristics of various social groups. The third is to take into account the diversity of manifestations of national psychic characteristics of individuals - not only to comprehensively understand and correctly interpret their entire complex and uniqueness, but also to systematically study each of them. Fourth, in the analysis of non-governmental, non-profit organizations, national-cultural centers, it is necessary to take into account that ethno-identity is known only through comparison and comparison with the same characteristics of representatives of other communities.

The analysis of the psychological aspects of the formation of ethnic identity in children of heteroethnic families has repeatedly become the subject of empirical research. Our research, which was conducted in order to study the psychological aspects of the manifestation of ethnic identity in children born on the basis of marriages of different nationalities, was conducted in three stages:

1. Identification stage (study of ethnic identity of teenagers);
2. Formative stage (choice of methodological tools for researching ethnic identity in adolescents);
3. Control stage (comparison of the results of experimental work).

In order to study the ethnic identity of teenagers, the following were used during our research: Dj. Finney's "Ethnic Identity Study" methodology, "Ethnic Identity Types" questionnaire (G.U.Soldatova, S.V. Rijova), O.L. Romanova's "Study of Ethnic Identity Characteristics of Children and Adolescents" scale. Relying on the above principles, the research organized by us was conducted at the meso level, in which teenage children of heteroethnic families living in the territory of our country participated as the object of research. Through the table given below, we can find out which heteronationality representatives of the objects that participated in our research.

According to the affective component of this methodology, the minimum value was 28 points, the average value was 12.09, the standard deviation was 7.51 points, and the excess showed a secret deviation to the left of -0.521. The minimum value of the integral index scale was 15 points, the maximum value was 48 points, the average value was 30.67, the standard deviation was 9.77 points, and the excess showed a secret deviation to the left of -1.087.

It is clear from the results presented above that the integral, i.e. general, indicator of the manifestation of ethnic identity is high in teenagers belonging to all ethnic groups, which allows us to conclude that their sense of belonging to their own nation is well developed.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

1. "Oila psixologiyasi" G'.B.Shoumarov, I.O.Haydarov, N.A.Sog'inov. Toshkent 2007y.130b.
2. Abduraxmonova Z. E., Nuraliyeva D. M. Formation of the concept of intelligence in foreign psychology //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – T. 11. – №. 3. – С. 852-857.
3. Berry J.W., Phinney J.S., Sam D.L., Vedder P. (2006) Immigrant Youth: Acculturation, Identity, and Adaptation. Applied Psychology: an International Review, 55(3): 303–332.
4. Binning K.R., Unzueta M.M., Huo Y.J., Molina L.E. (2009). The interpretation of multiracial status and its relation to social Engagement and psychological wellbeing. Journal of Social Issues, 65, 35–49.
5. Волкова А. Н. Социально-психологические факторы супружеской совместимости. -М.: Речь, 1997. - 236 с.
6. Farver J.M., Xu Y., Bhadha B.R., Narang S., Lieber E. (2007) Ethnic Identity, Acculturation, Parenting Beliefs, and Adolescent Adjustment: A Comparison of Asian Indian and European American Families. Merrill-Palmer Quarterly, 53(2):184–215.
7. Giok H. P. "Choose One!": Challenges of Inter-Ethnic Marriages in Malaysia / Giok Hun Pue & Nidzam Sulaiman. - Asian Social Science. - 2013. - Vol. 9. - No. 17. - P. 269278.
8. Nuraliyeva D. M. Examining the orientation of women in the field of psychosocial service for the family and the empirical analysis of psychological qualities. International scientific and practical conference Cutting Edge-science Primedia E-launch page115-116 . USA Conference Proceedings 2020/6
9. Nuraliyeva D. M. STUDYING SUSCEPTIBILITY TO THE BEHAVIOIR OF THE PAIR IN THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MAN AND WOMAN AND GIVING A SOCIAL-PSYCOLOGICAL HELP //Теория и практика современной науки. – 2018. – №. 5. – С. 32-34.
10. Nuraliyeva D. M. The problems of developing social psychological mechanisms in the family //Theoretical & Applied Science. – 2020. – №. 1. – С. 711-713.
11. Nuraliyeva D. M. THE PROBLEMS OF DEVELOPING SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGICAL MECHANISMS IN THE FAMILY //Theoretical & Applied Science. – 2020. – №. 1. – С. 711-713.
12. Nuraliyeva Dildora Mamurjonovna Psychological assistance to families on the verge of divorce 2021/10 "Экономика и социум" №10(89)
13. Nuraliyeva Dildora Mamurjonovna. The concept of psychological service and its controversial issues in family. Stran/34-36 Proceedings of International Conference on Multidisciplinary Sciences and Innovative Technologies Organized by Novateur Publications, India /2020/6/25.
14. Mamurjonovna N. D. The concept of psychological service and its controversial issues in family //Archive of Conferences. – 2020. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 34-36.
15. Нуралиева, Д. М. (2020). КОНЦЕПЦИЯ ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ СЛУЖБЫ СЕМЬИ. ББК Ю953, 405.
16. Nuraliyeva D. M. Examining the orientation of women in the field of psychosocial service for the family and the empirical analysis of psychological qualities //International scientific and practical conference Cutting Edge-science Primedia E-launch page115-116. USA Conference Proceedings. – 2020. – Т. 6.
17. Nuraliyeva D. M. THE PROBLEMS OF DEVELOPING SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGICAL MECHANISMS IN THE FAMILY //Theoretical & Applied Science. – 2020. – №. 1. – С. 711-713.
18. Nuraliyeva, D. M. (2020). THE PROBLEMS OF DEVELOPING SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGICAL MECHANISMS IN THE FAMILY. Theoretical & Applied Science, (1), 711-713.

19. Ma'murjonovna, N. D. (2020). Empirical analysis of the family responsibilities for psychological services in Uzbekistan. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(3), 278-282.
20. Nuraliyeva, D. M. (2018). STUDYING SUSCEPTIBILITY TO THE BEHAVIOUR OF THE PAIR IN THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MAN AND WOMAN AND GIVING A SOCIAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL HELP. *Теория и практика современной науки*, (5 (35)), 32-34.
21. Нуралиева, Д. М. (2022). ОСОБЕННОСТИ ОБЩЕНИЯ ДЕТЕЙ И РОДИТЕЛЕЙ В СЕМЕЙНЫХ ОТНОШЕНИЯХ. *Uzbek Scholar Journal*, 6, 39-43.
22. Mamurjonovna, Nuraliyeva Dildora. "PSYCHOLOGICAL SERVICE AND ITS ROLE IN FAMILY RELATIONSHIPS." (2022): 115-121.
23. Nuraliyeva, D. M. (2020). CHARACTERISTICS OF MARRIAGE RELATIONS IN PROVIDING PSYCHOLOGICAL AID TO THE FAMILY AND IT INFLUENCE ON THE STRENGTH OF MARRIAGE. In *Психологическое здоровье населения как важный фактор обеспечения процветания общества* (pp. 411-414).
24. Nuraliyeva D. M. Development of socio-psychological mechanisms of psychological services to families and children. – 2019.

